

**D5.6 First annual report on
dissemination activities to
international stakeholders**

**WP5 Science to policy
translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: SSI

Contributing partners: BfR, PMT members

GENERAL INFORMATION

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1. Summary

This report describes the dissemination activities of WP5 of One Health EJP during Y1. During Y1, contacts were established, website groups were formed, Kick-off Meeting and two Stakeholders Committee meetings were held, and dissemination strategy was compiled.

2. Highlights

- Contacts and dialogue established between the One Health EJP and the Key EU Stakeholders ECDC and EFSA (D5.1)
- Contacts established between specific projects within the One Health EJP and representatives of the Key EU Stakeholders ECDC and EFSA
- Kick-off Meeting and Two Stakeholders Committee meetings held
- Website groups for dissemination formed
- Concept for capacity map of WP5 developed (D5.4)
- Dissemination strategy to Stakeholders compiled (D5.5)

3. Description of the activities

Dissemination is defined as follows: “The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.” (EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

Focus in dissemination activities is on making results available so that they can be used. Dissemination is thus disclosure of the results in an attractive and user-friendly way. Dissemination is spreading the new knowledge as widely as possible – but in a targeted manner that focuses on target audiences that can make best use of the results. WP5 dissemination activities focus on the stakeholders.

WP5 dissemination activities are complementary to the general dissemination activities of the OHEJP (WP1). The general dissemination activities include e.g. that scientific publications and

other outcomes yielded by the One Health EJP will be made available on the website of the One Health EJP without delay (WP1). Stakeholders are encouraged to use these materials.

WP5 dissemination activities address specific groups: Key EU Stakeholders, Stakeholders Committee, and all stakeholders. The activities focus largely on facilitating diffusion and use of knowledge. Transactional aspects, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, are also included. Moreover, there are social change aspects: the EJP advocates One Health approach by enhancing and facilitating access and use of the One Health results.

During Y1, the dissemination activities focused on Key EU Stakeholders and Stakeholders Committee. The main contacts were established, website groups were formed, two Stakeholders Committee meetings were held, and Dissemination Strategy was compiled.

The main results disseminated were the list of priority topics for the second call for projects, which took into account the expressed research and integrative needs of the stakeholders, and the Letters of Intent for the second call, which were shared for information and for opportunity to provide feedback already at an early stage.

The dissemination activities continue actively in Y2. The projects will start to produce results that will be disseminated using the means described in Dissemination strategy (D5.5). Major dissemination activity will be the first Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM). The capacity map of WP5 (D5.4) will be one of the results for the One Health EJP to disseminate to the stakeholders. The first tailored reports will be produced in Y2, and the One Health EJP works towards including further stakeholders to the Stakeholders Committee.

4. Evaluation, impact and potential

The dissemination activities of Y1 have been mainly preparatory: establishing the contacts, forming online groups, and compiling the strategy for dissemination. The contacts established have been active and the platforms and structures for efficient dissemination are in place. Feedback has been positive, and an impact expressed is increased One Health -thinking: a more focused reflection on

internal structures already established for One Health collaborations as well as identification of options for further collaborations .

Efficient uptake and use of the results maximises the impact of the research. The Key EU stakeholders are in the position to have identified which gaps, when filled or bridged, can have the highest value for informing decision-making in EU to strengthen EU resilience the most. One Health EJP fills such gaps and efficient and timely dissemination of the results has major potential for impact.